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Data management plan (DMP)

Trend Analysis of Bitcoin and Classical Asset Prices: A Comparative Study

EOSCSecretariat.eu

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	10/05/2023	First version of DMP – created for start of project
2.0	12/05/2023	Update DMP – add DOI for produced data and repository
3.0	13/05/2023	Final version of DMP – prepared for midterm review

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	gold_bitcoin_dowJones_<date>.csv	Structured text	csv	1 MB	no

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Gold Prices	https://www.nasdaq.com/market-activity/commodities/gc:cmx/historical	None – public data	no
R2	Bitcoin Prices	https://api.coindesk.com/v1/bpi/historical/close.json?start=2010-07-17&end=2023-05-07	None – public data	no
R3	Dow Jones Index	https://query1.finance.yahoo.com/v7/finance/download/%5EDJI?period1=1271433600&period2=1651900800&interval=1d&events=history&includeAdjustedClose=true	None – public data	no

R1 contains the following columns: **Date**, **Close/Last**, Volume, Open, High, Low.

R2 contains the following data as json: **Date**, **price**.

R3 contains the following data: **Date**, Open, High, Low, **Close**, Adj Close, Volume.

The used data columns for the experiment are highlighted.

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The reused data (csv and json) will be processed in Python using the “pandas”-library by loading it into DataFrames, removing unused columns, calculating a mean per month, calculating a relative percentage change for each month, and aggregated into a new DataFrame which gets stored as a csv-file.

New Data can be added easily any time when new data is available if the reused data is in the required format.

Data provenance will be documented by providing the URL of the data source. All used data is publicly available.

The produced data P1 contains the following columns: Date, Price_Gold, Price_Bitcoin, Dow_Jones

Change in percentage is not included, as this information can be derived from the available data.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention as defined as: <description>_v<versionNo>_<YYYYMMDD> For example: bitcoinPrices_v1_20230510.json

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at project level. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

The README contains all required documentation needed to facilitate data reuse.

Generated data files follow the naming conventions defined as: <description>_<YYYYMMDD>

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: standardised data capture.

The data will not change in the future, as only historical data is considered.

The quality of the data can be assured as the data is publicly available.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project leader. Private infrastructure will be used for this purpose.

P1 (gold_bitcoin_dow.csv), R1 (Gold Prices), R2 (Bitcoin Prices), R3 (Dow Jones Index) will be stored in Microsoft OneDrive.

A backup of the data will also be stored in the project's repository at GitHub. Additionally, the reused data is publicly available via the provided URLs.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

In case of an incident, the reused data can be recovered from one of the two alternative storages provided. Everyone has access to the research data.

The generated data will be backed up after each run, additionally GitHub provides version history of each file including the generated data.

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only
R3	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	Open	2023-05-13	TU Wien Research Data	10.70124/c70yb-q6d73	CC BY 4.0

The repositories used in this project are described in the following paragraph:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and

publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

The data will not be updated after the final delivery on May 13th, 2023. The data can be used in compliance with the CC BY 4.0 licence.

Methods or software needed to access and use data: To access the data, no specific tools are required as it is in the standardized form of a csv file.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

The decision is that the data should only be preserved in form of a csv-file. All other data which include representations of the data in form of plots will be deleted after the project.

The reason for this decision is that the plot does not hold any additional valuable information.

Possible research uses are to compare future price developments with the observed period in this project and to accept or reject the hypothesis that the price of bitcoin correlates with the price of gold or if the observed period does not follow any particular correlation.

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Students and general public

Overview of (unpublished) data that will be deleted:

dataset ID	kind/name of data	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person
G1	Plot comparing raw data	May 13 th 2023	Graphical representation of data	Simon Schwantler
G2	Plot showing relative price changes	May 13 th 2023	Graphical representation of data	Simon Schwantler
G3	Plot showing trend analysis	May 13 th 2023	Graphical representation of data	Simon Schwantler

The source code will be preserved at github:

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	PID/DOI	foreseeable research uses and/or users
R1	github	10 years	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7928416	Students and general public

5c Data access

There are no specific tools required to access and use the data, as the csv-file can be opened in any editor. To process the data, there is no limitation on any specific tool or programming language, as long as it is possible to parse csv files.

To re-run the experiment, python is required with the packages stated in the requirements file in the repository.

5d Unique and persistent identifiers

PIDs are provided for the produced dataset and the repository:

Source Code	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7928416
Dataset	https://doi.org/10.70124/c70yb-q6d73

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The Project Lead will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The lead country researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.